

1 **Low molecular weight reduced sulfur substances: a major** 2 **component of non-volatile dissolved organic sulfur in the Pacific** 3 **Ocean**

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17 18 **Supporting Information**

19 20 *Material and methods*

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22 All the solutions as well as the washing of the material was performed with ultrapure water
23 from a purification system, Milli-Q Element (resistivity > 18.2 MΩ) from Millipore®.

24 25 *Sampling*

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27 Samples were collected during the cruise GEOTRACES US-GP15 (53.67°N – 20°S; 156.93°W
28 – 152°W, onboard the R/V Roger Revelle between September and November 2018). The
29 seawater was collected using the Oceanographic Data Facility's (ODF, Scripps Institution of
30 Oceanography) CTD rosette equipped with twelve 30 L Niskin bottles. Samples were filtered
31 through 0.8/0.45 μm Acropak 500 filter cartridges and were stored in a -20°C freezer until
32 analysis.

33 34 *Analysis of thioacetamide-like (TA-like) compounds*

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36 Reduced sulfur species (RSS) such as thioacetamide (TA) form strong complexes with metals
37 (Hansen & Winther, 2009) and are thus detectable by adsorptive cathodic stripping
38 voltammetric (Ad-CSV) at the surface of a mercury drop electrode (Quentel et al., 1986). The
39 analysis of TA-like compounds was performed following the recommendations of Pernet-
40 Coudrier et al. (2013). The TA concentration was determined by the standard addition method
41 (example for a surface sample in Figure S1) using commercial TA (ACS reagent, Sigma-

Figure S1. Analysis of thioacetamide (TA) compounds by Ad-CSV (60 s deposition time) by the standard addition method at pH 2, in 7.1 mL of seawater (depth 55.7 m) from the Central Eastern Pacific Ocean (GEOTRACES US-GP15 - 2018). Non-visible error bars on the right are covered by the symbols.

42 Aldrich, Switzerland, $\geq 99\%$) in ultrapure water ($132 - 140 \mu\text{M}$). Before analysis, the sample
 43 was introduced into a glass voltammetric cell, washed beforehand with acidified ultrapure water
 44 (pH 2, HCl), to limit any risk of contamination. 7.00 ± 0.01 g of water were weighed directly
 45 into the cell under laminar flow hood before lowering the pH to 2 by adding $\sim 70 \mu\text{L}$ of a diluted
 46 HCl solution ($\sim 1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$). Measurements were performed using a three-electrode
 47 electrochemical device (Metrohm model 663 VA) connected to a potentiostat/galvanostat
 48 ($\mu\text{Autolab}^\circledast$ Type III, Utrecht, Holland), controlled by GPES 4.9 software. The working
 49 electrode was a Static Mercury Drop Electrode (SMDE) with a drop size of $\sim 0.52 \text{ mm}^2$. An
 50 Ag/AgCl electrode (salt bridge in $\text{KCl } 3 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, Suprapur $^\circledast$, Merck) and a glassy carbon
 51 electrode were used as reference and counter (auxiliary) electrodes respectively. After a
 52 degassing step under stirring (60 s, N_2 99.99%), the "Hg-(TA) $_2$ " complex adsorbed on the
 53 working electrode (Figure S2) under the application of a potential of 0 V for a duration
 54 depending on the TA concentration in the sample (60 – 120 s). The redissolution of the
 55 complexes deposited on the electrode occurs during the cathodic scan in differential pulse mode
 56 from 0 to -0.6 V. According to Pernet-Coudrier et al. (2013), a reproducibility of 12% ($n = 8$)
 57 and a repeatability of 3.3% ($n = 11$) were calculated. For deposition times of 60 s and 300 s,
 58 limits of detection were estimated to be 81 nmol L^{-1} and 22 nmol L^{-1} , respectively.

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60 ***Carbon to sulfur (C:S) ratios of bulk and low molecular weight (LMW)***
 61 ***dissolved organic matter (DOM)***

Figure S2. Probable mechanism of $\text{Hg}-(\text{S}-\text{R})_2$ complex formation by adsorption at the surface of the mercury drop.

63 The concentrations of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) were then measured by size exclusion
 64 chromatography (SEC) coupled with an organic carbon detector (OCD) (DOC-Labor®,
 65 Karlsruhe, Germany). All the chemicals (mobile/acid phases) for SEC were prepared following
 66 the protocol from Huber et al. (2011). The data treatment was also done in the same way as
 67 these authors. The calibration of the OCD was performed as Dulaquais et al. (2018) which adapt
 68 DOC measurement by SEC for marine waters. The SEC device, equipped with two
 69 chromatographic columns (250 mm × 20 mm, TSK HW-50S, 3000 theoretical plates, Toso,
 70 Japan), permits the separation of dissolved organic matter (DOM) into five fractions of organic
 71 compounds with an optimal resolution. All the DOC concentrations measured within each
 72 fraction of each sample largely exceeded the limits of detection determined by Dulaquais et al.
 73 (2018) for marine waters. Deep seawater reference (DSR) samples used to validate the DOC
 74 measurements were provided by the *Hansell* research laboratory ($\text{DOC}_{\text{DSR}} = 43.2 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{mol}$
 75 L^{-1} ; $n = 5$; consensus value of lot #10 – 18: 43 – 45 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$).

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77 The electrochemical method applied to the detection of TA type compounds is based on the
 78 sulfur-mercury reaction within the $\text{Hg}-(\text{S}-\text{R})_2$ complex. This complex is formed on the surface
 79 of the mercury drop (measuring electrode) according to the scheme presented in Figure S2. The
 80 electron sharing of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ double bond towards the electron gap of the Hg^{2+} ion (Figure S2A)
 81 and then the adsorption of the $\text{Hg}-(\text{S}-\text{R})_2$ complex formed (Figure S2B) to the mercury drop

82 (Figure S2C) involves one electron (e^-) per sulfur atom. The current is thus directly proportional
83 to the number of sulfur atoms. This implies that even if species other than TA-type compounds
84 are detected at the measurement potential, the assay is only representative of sulfur. A study of
85 the sulfur component of DOM can therefore be conducted from the elemental ratio of
86 carbon:sulfur (C:S) quantitatively from the concentrations of DOC determined by SEC and TA-
87 like compounds determined by Ad-CSV.
88 The commercial solution of TA used for the standard additions for electrochemical analyses
89 was analyzed by SEC to identify the fraction of DOC containing this type of compound. An
90 average retention time of TA of 157 minutes in the steric exclusion columns was evidenced
91 (Figure S3). In accordance with the operational definition of the bounds for the organic
92 compound fractions of DOM (Huber et al., 2011), the TA-type compounds analyzed by Ad-
93 CSV were identified as LMW neutral molecules. An estimate of the sulfur composition of
94 marine DOM could therefore be calculated in the fraction of LMW neutrals, from successive
95 analysis of the same samples by SEC and Ad-CSV.

Figure S3. Chromatogram of the carbon of commercial thioacetamide (TA) (ACS reagent, Sigma-Aldrich, Switzerland, $\geq 99\%$) by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) in ultrapure water.

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